

SAMPLE INFORMATION

Sample Name:	LRM-4-118-IG-1% RAC	Acquired By:	System
Sample Type:	Unknown	Sample Set Name:	
Vial:	10	Acq. Method Set:	1%210400
Injection #:	1	Processing Method:	LRM 4 118
Injection Volume:	3.00 ul	Channel Name:	254.0nm
Run Time:	100.0 Minutes	Proc. Chnl. Descr.:	2998 PDA 254.0 nm (2998)
Date Acquired:	11/17/2022 8:06:51 PM CST		
Date Processed:	3/8/2023 8:29:53 PM CST		

	RT	Area	% Area	Height
1	20.383	6540790	49.51	190513
2	21.939	6669031	50.49	171937

SAMPLE INFORMATION

Sample Name:	LRM-4-117-IG-1% ASY	Acquired By:	System
Sample Type:	Unknown	Sample Set Name:	
Vial:	10	Acq. Method Set:	1%210400
Injection #:	1	Processing Method:	LRM 4 117
Injection Volume:	3.00 ul	Channel Name:	254.0nm
Run Time:	25.0 Minutes	Proc. Chnl. Descr.:	2998 PDA 254.0 nm (2998)
Date Acquired:	11/18/2022 9:56:16 AM CST		
Date Processed:	3/8/2023 8:30:10 PM CST		

	RT	Area	% Area	Height
1	19.973	16811310	97.98	457450
2	21.441	346424	2.02	9234